

A Theoretical Novel Design Approach To Enhance The Evaporator Steam Economy Of Large Scale Sugar Industries In Ethiopia

M. Sathiyamoorthy, Department of Chemical Engineering, College of Engineering, Defence University, Debrezeit, Ethiopia, North East Africa

Amanuel Gebrekrstos, Department of Chemical Engineering, College of Engineering, Defence University, Debrezeit, Ethiopia, North East Africa

G.Balachandran, Department of Chemical Engineering, Mekelle University, Mekelle, Ethiopia, North East Africa.

Abstract

The sugar industries are one of the major food industries in all countries in terms of demand, capacity and consumption. According to the Ethiopian country's statistical report, the demand of sugar is tremendously increasing. To meet the demand and the requirements of sugar, many sugar industries are established. The existing sugar industries are operating with high steam consumption and less production capacity. The major cost and energy loss in the sugar industries are the consumption of steam. The main challenging objective in the sugar industry is to reduce the steam consumption. Most of the sugar industries in Ethiopia are using rising film calendria type multiple effect evaporators (Robert's type evaporator) which are simple, robust, and easy to operate but are susceptible to scaling and require periodic cleaning. The scaling highly reduces the heat transfer, which make the multi effect evaporator to consume more amount of steam. This research work suggests that the rising film multi effect evaporator can be replaced by some radial type multi effect evaporator, which can eliminate the disadvantages caused by the rising film evaporator. This replacement modification can reduce the steam consumption in the process. The design modifications are done for the large capacity of 4000 TCD (tones cane per day). This novel design approach shows that the steam economy can be enhanced in the large scale sugar industries of Ethiopia

Keywords: Steam economy, steam consumption, sugar industries, evaporators, design modification, multi effect evaporator, rising film evaporator, radial type evaporator, Robert's evaporator.

1. Introduction

A. Evaporation

The objective of evaporation is to concentrate a solution consisting of a non-volatile solute and a volatile solvent. In the overwhelming majority of evaporations the solvent is water. Evaporation differs from drying in that the residue is a liquid sometimes a highly viscous one rather than a solid; it differs from distillation in that the vapor usually is a single component, and even when the vapor is a mixture, no attempt is made in the evaporation step to separate the vapor into fractions; it differs from in that the emphasis is placed on concentrating a solution rather than forming and building crystals. Normally in evaporation the thick liquor is the valuable product and the vapor is condensed and discarded.

B. Liquid characteristics

The practical solution of an evaporation problem is profoundly affected by the character of the liquor to be evaporated. It is the wide variation in liquor to be concentrated. Some of the most important properties of evaporating liquids are as follows:

Concentration: Although the thin liquor fed to an evaporator may be sufficiently dilute to have many of the physical properties of water, as the concentration increases, the solution becomes more and more individualistic. The density and viscosity increase with solid content until either the solution becomes saturated

or the liquor becomes sluggish for adequate heat transfer. Continued boiling of a saturated solution causes crystals to form; these must be removed or the tubes clog. The boiling point of a solution may also rise considerably as the solid content increases, so that the boiling temperature of a concentrated solution may be much higher than that of water at the same pressure.

Foaming: Some materials, especially organic substances, foam during vaporization. Stable foam accompanies the vapor out of the evaporator, causing heavy entrainment. In extreme cases the entire mass of liquid may boil over into the vapor outlet and be lost. Temperature sensitivity: Many fine chemicals, pharmaceutical products and foods are damaged when heated to moderate temperatures for relatively short times. In concentrating such materials special techniques are needed to reduce both the temperature of the liquid and the time of heating.

Scale: Some solutions deposit scale on the heating surfaces. The overall coefficient then steadily diminishes, until the evaporator must be shut down and the tubes cleaned. When the scale is hard and insoluble, the cleaning is difficult and expensive.

C. Types of evaporator

The specialized equipments in which the evaporation process is carried out in industries are called evaporators. Different kinds of evaporators are designed for various purposes whose classification is given in the diagram.

Figure 1. Evaporator classification

Most evaporators are heated by steam condensing on metal tubes. Nearly always the material to be evaporated flows through the tubes. Usually the steam is at a low pressure; often the boiling liquid is under a moderate vacuum. Reducing the boiling temperature of liquid increases the temperature difference between the steam and the boiling liquid and thereby increases the heat transfer rate in the evaporator.

When a single evaporator is used, the vapor from the boiling liquid is condensed and discarded. This method is called single-effect evaporation; although it is simple it utilizes steam ineffectively if the vapor from one evaporator is fed into the steam chest of a second evaporator and the vapor from is second is then sent to the condenser, the operation becomes double effect. The heat in the original steam is reused. Hence with the same amount of steam the amount of water evaporated is almost doubled. Additional effects can be added in the same manner. The general method of increasing the evaporation per one kilogram of steam by using series of evaporators between the steam supply and the condenser is called multiple effect evaporation. The major types of steam heated tubular evaporators in use are, 1. Short tube evaporators. 2. Long tube evaporators.

Short tube evaporators: These are the older types of evaporators in which tubes of length 4 to 8 feet and 2 to 4 inch in diameter are employed. In short tube vertical

evaporators steam condenses outside the tubes. The tube bundle contains a large central downcomer, the cross sectional area of which is 25 to 40 percent of the total cross sectional area of the tubes. Most of the boiling takes place in the tubes, so that liquid rises through the tubes and returns through the downcomer, the vapor formed escapes from the vapor outlet at the top the tail space above the tubes. In this kind of evaporators the driving force for the flow of liquid through the tubes is the difference in density between the liquid in the downcomer and the mixture of liquid and vapor in the tubes. Short-tube evaporators provide moderately good heat transfer at reasonable cost. They are fairly effective with scaling liquids; the inside of the tubes can be easily cleaned. Circulation is by natural convection but at a much less rapid rate than in long-tube natural circulation evaporators; the heat transfer coefficients, therefore, are fairly high with thin liquids but low when liquid is viscous. Once considered as “standard” evaporators, short-tube vertical units have been largely displaced by long-tube evaporators and other more specialized designs.

Long tube evaporators with upward flow: The essential parts of this system are (1) a tubular exchanger with steam in the shell and liquid to be concentrated in the tubes, (2) a separator or vapor space removing entrained liquid from the vapor, and (3) when operated as a circulation unit, a return leg for the liquid from the separator to the bottom of the exchanger. Inlets are provided for feed liquid and steam and outlets are provided for vapor, thick liquor, steam condensate, and non condensable gases from the steam. Liquid and vapor flow upward inside the tubes as a result of the boiling action; separated enter to the bottom of the tubes by gravity. Dilute feed, often at about room temperature, enters the system and mixes with liquid returning from the separator. The mixture enters the bottom of the tubes flows upward as liquid, receiving heat from the steam. Bubbles then form in the liquid as boiling begin, increasing the linear velocity and rate of heat transfer. Near the top of the tubes the bubbles grow rapidly. In this zone bubbles of vapor alternating with slugs of liquid rise very quickly through the tubes and emerge at high velocity at the top.

From the tubes the mixture of liquid of liquid and vapors enter the separator. The diameter of separator is larger than that of exchanger, so that the linearly velocity of the vapor is greatly reduced. As a further aid in eliminating water droplets the vapor impinges on, and then passes

around, sets of baffle plates before leaving the separator. These are especially effective in concentrating liquids that tend to foam. Foam is broken when high-velocity mixture of liquid and vapor impinges against the vapor-head baffle.

Multiple effect evaporators: If an evaporator is fed with steam of total heat of 100 kJ/kg and it is evaporating water at 373 K, then each kg of water vapor produced will have a total heat of 97 kJ. If this heat is allowed to go waste, by condensing it in a tubular condenser or by direct contact in a jet condenser, such a system makes very poor use of steam. The vapor produced is, however, suitable for passing to the calandria of a similar unit, provided the boiling temperature in the second unit is reduced so that an adequate temperature difference is maintained. This can be affected by applying vacuum to the second effect in order to reduce the boiling point of the liquor. This is the principle reached in the multiple effect systems, which were introduced by Rillieux in about 1830.

Consider the three evaporators arranged in which the temperatures and pressures are as $T_1, T_2, T_3,$ and $P_1, P_2, P_3,$ respectively, in each unit. Suppose the liquor has no boiling point rise, and that effects of hydrostatic head can be neglected. Then the heat transmitted per unit time across each effect will be.

Effect 1	$Q_1=U_1A_1\Delta T_1$
Effect 2	$Q_2=U_2A_2\Delta T_2$
Effect 3	$Q_3=U_3A_3\Delta T_3$

Neglecting the heat required to heat the T_f the feed temperature of the liquor to T_1 , the Q_1 transferred across A_1 appears as latent heat in vapor. Hence,

$$Q_1=Q_2=Q_3$$

$$U_1A_1\Delta T_1=U_2A_2\Delta T_2=U_3A_3\Delta T_3$$

If, as is commonly the case, the individual effects are alike, $A_1=A_2=A_3,$ so that:

$$U_1\Delta T_1=U_2\Delta T_2=U_3\Delta T_3$$

On this analysis, the difference in temperature across each effect is inversely proportional to the heat transfer coefficient. This, however, represents a simplification, since (a) the heat required to heat feed from T_f to T_1 has been neglected, and (b) the liquor passing from 1 to 2

carries heat into the second effect, and this is responsible for some evaporation; similarly for the third effect. The latent heat required to evaporate 1kg of water in 1, is approximately equal to the heat obtained in condensing 1kg of steam thus 1kg of steam fed to 1 evaporates 1kg of water in 1. Again the 1kg of steam from evaporates about 1kg of steam in 2. Thus, in N effect system, 1kg of steam fed to the first effect will evaporate in all about N kilograms of liquid. The great attractions of the multiple effect system are the more evaporation per kilogram of steam is obtained than in single effect unit.

The water evaporated in each effect is proportional to Q, since the latent heat is sensibly constant. Thus the total capacity of system is:

$$Q=Q_1+Q_2+Q_3$$

$$U_1A_1\Delta T_1+U_2A_2\Delta T_2+U_3A_3\Delta T_3$$

If an average value of coefficients is taken, then:

$$Q = U_{avg} (\Delta T_1+\Delta T_2+\Delta T_3) A$$

assuming the area of each effect is same. A single effect evaporator operating with same temperature difference ΔT , with this average coefficient U_{avg} , would, however, have the same $Q=U_{avg} * A * \Delta T$. Thus, it is seen that capacity of a multiple effect system is the same as that of a single effect operating with same temperature difference and having area 'A' equal to that of one of the multiple effect units, but a very large temperature difference is to be maintained. The value of the multiple effect system is that better use is made of steam though, in order to bring this about, it is necessary to make a much bigger capital outlay for the increased number of units and accessories.

2. Process In Cane Preparation

A. Cane preparation

Modern practice has demonstrated that efficient recovery of sugar (sucrose) from the sugar cane is only possible if we separate the function of cane preparation from that of juice extraction. Because the walls of the cells which contain the juice within the tissue of cane are impermeable, it is necessary to rupture as many of the cells as possible during the preparation phase. The efficiency of this preparation may be determined as a comparative ratio of juice brix. This ratio as a percentage is often referred to as a preparation index (PI) or the

displaceability index (DI). The good juice extraction is only achieved if the PI is above 90, such a high degree of preparation can only be achieved by the use of heavy duty hammer-type shredders. Such shredders usually have an installed power of 7-10 kW per ton.

In order to present an even flow of cane to the shredder and hence to obtain an even utilization of power, it is necessary to break whole stalk cane into smaller pieces before the shredding operation. This can be done by conventional cane knives or by a billeting process which shears the stalks into sections about 20cm long. It is important that all the cane is billeted or knifed as it is difficult to feed any uncut cane without causing an obstruction at the shredder inlet.

B. Juice extraction

There are two separate methods of extracting juice from sugar cane. Still the most common is milling; where the cane is passed through a series of rollers arranged to give a sequence of multiple compressions to express the juice. Within this sequence water is added normally in front of the last mill and the juice extracted is applied in contra-flow to the cane. This addition of water and subsequently of dilute extracted juice is called imbibition. Individual mills can have three, four, five or six compression rollers and a number of individual mills arranged in series are called a mill tandem. It is usual for a mill tandem to have from four to seven individual mills.

This second method of juice extraction, now more widely used, is called diffusion because the cell wall in sugar cane is not permeable, the purist may prefer the term lixiviation or leaching. However, the word diffusion is universally applied to this process and so custom and practice prevail. This method of juice extraction relies on sequential washing of a bed of well prepared cane by a hot and dilute liquid, again in contra-flow to the cane. Because the ratio of liquid to cane is much greater than that normally used in milling, this liquid is called recirculation juice. This is the sum of the imbibition water added to the diffuser and press water returned from the dewatering mills.

The diffusion process is itself sub-divided into;

- a) Bagasse diffusion – where there is pre-extraction of juice in a single mill prior to lixiviation.
- b) Cane diffusion – where there is no pre-extraction of juice before the lixiviation process.

C. Clarification

Clarification of the juice, that is the settling out of suspended non-sugars, is done most commonly by the addition of milk of lime and by heating to 100°C & more. This is called the **defecation process**. Careful control of the temperature and the pH levels allows the suspended matter to conglomerate and the muds to settle out. This happens more efficiently in well designed subsiders or clarifiers. To improve the rate of settling a small quantity of polyelectrolyte is added to the limed and heated juice immediately before it enters the clarifier.

The lime mixed with water to produce a suspension called 'milk of lime' whose density is maintained constant. Therefore the quantity of limed juice is practically the same as the quantity of raw juice. The clarifier muds are mixed with Bagacillo and desweetened by washing on rotary vacuum filters. The required surface area of the filters varies greatly from country to country but an average figure based on a hourly throughput rate would be 60 m² per 100 tons of cane. Filtrates from the rotary vacuum filters are returned to the weighed juice tank, averaging about 15% of the raw juice flow. Thus the total quantity of limed juice (raw juice + filtrate + milk of lime) to the clarifier is about 116 tons per 100 tons of cane.

D. Evaporation

It is obvious that the quantity of clear juice leaving the clarifier will be the arithmetical difference between the quantity of juice entering the clarifier and the quantity of mud going to the filter station for sweetening off. The desweetened mud, now semi-dry and often called filter cake, discharged from the filters is about 5% on cane which is a good rule of thumb average, and the quantity of water for sweetening off is 7% on cane. This gives a filtrate return on 15% on cane. The sugar loss in filter cake will lie normally between 1% and 2% weight of cake. The quantity of clarified juice going forward to the evaporator will be in the order of 105t to 108t clear juice per 100 t cane. For our future calculations we will use a figure of 110t of clear juice which will allow a sufficient safety margin. Because mud volumes vary enormously from country to country and factory to factory, the figures given above must be regarded as only typical and should be used with care.

E. Raw sugar and final molasses

The total solids, sucrose and impurities (ash, reducing sugars etc) contained in the clarified juice will travel

through the whole process and, disregarding losses, will finally appear in the form of only two products, which are raw sugar and final molasses. It has already been assumed in the previous process that the clarified juice contains 14.4 ton solids with a sucrose content of 11.5 ton. The raw sugar produced is about 96% and the composition of the final molasses would indicate a true purity in the order of 32%. However it is now much more common to produce raw sugar at 98% because of refiners demand for better quality.

F. Steam requirements for the process

Because of the emphasis now being placed on the conservation of energy, modern or modernized factories are designed for good thermal efficiency, so that they may be self-sufficient on bagasse fuel only and be able to export electrical power in parallel with the production of sugar during the crop. The steam raising plant and the equipment required to drive the machinery for the extraction of juice and for the generation of electrical energy, must be carefully chosen to obtain a good balance between initial cost and operating efficiency. As a result, there has been a progressive increase in steam boiler pressures and temperatures. The choice of steam boiler operating pressure is governed by the capability to operate and control sophisticated boiler feed water quality requirements. The total capacity of the electrical generating plant will have a strong influence on the choice of the boiler installation. Where high electrical export loads are envisaged the boiler pressures will probably be between 87-110 bar and for the smaller factories between 25-30 bar. Modern boiler plant produces steam at a total temperature between 350-400°C. Temperatures higher than this require the use of expensive alloy steels for super heater tubes and for live steam piping.

G. Evaporators

A well designed and competently operated evaporator is very flexible and adapts itself automatically to greatly varying working conditions. As it is now general practice to arrange for evaporators to be bled to provide vapour for heating vacuum pans and juice heater.

There are large and often unpredictable variations in the coefficient of heat transfer which occur in an individual body; these are mainly due to the formation of scale and to the effect of increasing viscosity of the syrup. Because of the vapour pressures, and hence temperatures, will adjust themselves automatically between the bodies. This adjustment will depend on the ability of the

respective vessels to condense vapors on the steam side of the calandria. Thus it is the calandria in the last body that exerts overall control in the operation of any given multiple effect evaporators. It is important therefore, when sizing an evaporator, to make a generous allowance for the effect of scaling which will be heaviest in the last body. Otherwise the operation of the whole evaporator will be constrained.

H. Rillieux principle

- i) Rillieux utilized the latent heat produced from evaporating sugar cane juice by employing a series of more than two evaporating pans.
- ii) Here vapour was piped out of each pan to heat the material in the next, with the vapors in the end going to a condenser.
- iii) At the same time, pressure in the system was reduced, which created partial vacuums and lowered the boiling point of the liquid.
- iv) According to Rillieux principle,
 - a) 'x' quantity of steam can generate 'nx' quantity of steam. Where n is the number of effects.
 - b) Steam economy = $\frac{n}{m} * x$, where n – nth effect from which vapour is bled
m- total no of effects
 - c) NCG (Non Combustible Gases) has to be removed from the process steam to meet the required heating with high efficiency.

Cogeneration: Sequential production of process heat and electricity to export with same fuel is termed as cogeneration. In sugar industry the co-generation is of topping cycle which is the steam generated is fed to the turbo generator and extracted at desired pressure for process. The benefits of cogeneration are the fuel; bagasse is renewable source of energy. There will be simultaneous power generation and process heating. The sugar industry generates additional power with the bagasse which is used for generation of steam to meet process requirements, results in reduced emission levels and global warming and is therefore environment friendly. It ensures fuel security. Cogeneration project leads to reduction in transmission losses considerably and thus helps in stabilizing the grid voltage because of their proximity to the load centers.

I. Energy conservation in sugar industries

- a) Ethiopian sugar industries are highly energy-intensive.
- b) Energy efficiency is well below that of other industrialized countries.

- c) Energy conservation measures shall lead to reduction in cost of production.

Potential for reduction in steam consumption

- i) Reduction in direct steam leakages.
- ii) Insulation of bare pipes flanges and valves etc, to reduce surface temperature 55°C.
- iii) Reduction in redundant steam pipelines.
- iv) Pressure control and syrup Brix control in the evaporator section.
- v) Adequate changes in steam and juice piping to ensure juice heating from different bodies of evaporator.
- vi) Application of continuous crystallizers for A B & C massecuites and continuous centrifugals for B & C curing, high gravity/high capacity batch centrifugals for a curing etc.
- vii) Rationalization of operations of minimizes fluctuations in steam demand.

3. Material Balance For Sugar Plant

The material balance for the sugar industries is given with a 4000 tones cane per day. The standard value in common sugar industries has been used for many calculations.

Basis: 4000 tones cane per day

1. Milling

<u>Input</u>	
Cane	- 181818.18 kg/hr
Fiber content-	14% on cane
Poll content -	12.34
Imbibitions water	56000 kg/hr
<u>Output</u>	
Mixed juice -	185870.13 kg/hr
Brix content -	14.3
Purity	- 80%
Bagasse	- 51948.05 kg/hr
Moisture content	48%
Fiber content-	49%

2. Screening tank

<u>Input</u>	
Mixed Juice -	185870.13 kg /hr
Phosphate slurry-	90.91 kg/hr
Filtrate from vacuum filter-	29472.73 kg
<u>Output</u>	
Raw juice	

3. Sulphur burner

<u>Input</u>	
Sulphur and air	
<u>Output</u>	
SO ₂ -	90.91 kg/hr

4. Lime slacker

<u>Input</u>	:	Lime & water
<u>Output</u>	:	2727.27 kg/hr of milk of lime

5. Juice sulphiter

<u>Input</u>	
Raw juice, SO ₂ -	90.91 kg/hr
Milk of lime -	2727.27 kg/hr
<u>Output</u>	
Sulphited juice -	218251.95 kg/hr

6. Sulphited juice heater

<u>Input</u>	
Sulphited juice -	218251.95 kg/hr
<u>Output</u>	
Flash	- 1818.77 kg/hr

7. Clarification

<u>Input</u>	
Sulphited juice	
Flocculent -	480 kg/hr
<u>Output</u>	
Muddy juice -	25236.36 kg/hr
Clear juice -	191676.82 kg/hr
Brix of clear juice	13.81

8. Purification of muddy juice

<u>Input</u>	
Muddy juice -	25236.36 kg/hr
Bagacillo -	1272.73 kg/hr
The mixer is passed through the vacuum filter, and then water is added at the rate of 8909.09 kg	
<u>Output</u>	
Filtrate	- 29472.73 kg/hr
Filter cake -	5945.45 kg/hr
The filtrate is sent to the screened juice tank	

9. Evaporators

<u>Input</u>	
Clear juice -	191676.82 kg/hr
Brix	- 13.81
It is sent through a series of evaporators (Quintuple effect)	
<u>Output</u>	
Conc.Syrup -	44687.10 kg/hr

10. Syrup sulphiter

<u>Input</u>	
Unsulphite syrup -	44723.47 kg/hr
SO ₂	- 36.36 kg/hr
<u>Output</u>	
Sulphited syrup	

Sulphited syrup enters pan supply tank and then to the syrup tank at the rate of 44723.47 kg/hr.

11. Syrup tank

<u>Input</u>	-	Syrup
<u>Output</u>	-	Syrup

Here the syrup is sent to the vacuum pan, from this 48856.59 kg/hr of juice is sent to the crystallizer & 20985.6 kg/hr of vapour is evaporated.

12. Crystallization

Input

Syrup	-	48856.59 kg/hr
Brix	-	93%
Purity	-	87%

Output
A-Massecuite which is sent in to the pug mill for mixing

13. Centrifugation

Input
A-Massecuite -1907.27 kg/hr of wash water

Output

Conc. juice	-	8446.54 kg/hr
A-Molasses	-	23955.28 kg/hr
Sugar crystals	-	20114.48 kg/hr

20114.48 kg/hr of Sugar crystals is sent into hopper, from the hopper it is sent to Cleated conveyor & then to grader.

The output from the grader consists of lumps,

Fine	-	1041.02 kg/hr
Brix content	-	99.96%
Purity	-	99.84%

14. Molasses conditioning

Input

Molasses	-	23955.28 kg/hr
Water	-	3422.18 kg/hr

Output
Conc. Syrup - 3691.64 kg/hr which is sent to A- Heavy, and the other part to vacuum pan.

15. Vacuum pan

Input

A-molasses		
Water	-	1818.18 kg/hr

Output

B-Massecuite		
Vapour	-	8233.09 kg/hr

The conc. syrup is sent to the crystallizer and then to the pug mill, followed by centrifugal (B)

1. From the centrifugal (B), 2 parts are separated. One part is sent to the molasses conditioner (2) & the other to the magma mixer.
2. From the magma mixer, 4080.92 kg/hr of mixed magma is sent to the B-seed crystallizer & the other to the melter.
3. From the centrifugal (B), 17270.91 kg/hr of crystals with 96% Brix & 71.92% purity is sent to molasses conditioner (2).
4. 12375.84 kg/hr of crystals is sent to B-Heavy.

5. A-Heavy & B-heavy are sent to the vacuum pan, where 8439.20 kg/hr of vapour is evaporated.
6. Then, the conc. Syrup is sent to crystallizer with the Brix content of 100% & 53%. It is sent into the pug mill, & to the centrifugal (C).
7. Here, one part is sent to the molasses storage tank at the rate of 8258.70 kg/hr with 90% Brix content & 30% purity, the other part is sent to the magma mixer.
8. 6140.63 kg/hr of sugar magma is sent to the pug mill, similarly, from the pug mill, it is sent to the centrifugal (D), where is water added along with it.
9. The molasses obtained from the centrifugal (D) is sent to the molasses conditioner at a rate of 2506.73 kg/hr with 96% Brix content & 82% purity. 2972.27 kg/hr of water is added to the molasses conditioner.
10. Molasses from the molasses conditioner (3) is sent to C-light.
11. C-light is added to the vacuum pan along with A-Heavy & B-Heavy and the process is continued.
12. The partially obtained sugar crystals from the centrifugal (D) are sent to the magma mixer.

16. Melting

Input

Magma (from B-Centrifugal)	-	3973.35 kg/hr
Brix	-	96%
Purity	-	94%
Steam	-	1041.02 kg/hr
Water	-	3496.04 kg/hr
Magma (from A-Heavy)	-	4080.92 kg/hr

Output

Melted sugar	-	12591.33 kg/hr
--------------	---	----------------

This melted sugar is passed into melt, where the process continues by adding it into the vacuum pan along with A-Light, Syrup, B-Seed sugar.

4. Steam Usage For Existing Robert Type Evaporator

Basis: 4000 TCD

Working hours:	4000/24 = 166.66 tons/hr
Mixed juice	= 105%
Sulphite juice	= 120%
Clear juice	= 105%

i) Raw juice heating stage 1

Quantity of vapour required
 = [166 * 1.05 * 0.9 * (40 - 30)]/563.3
 = 2.79 MT/hr

ii) Raw juice heating stage 2

Condensate heating at 35 - 60°C
 = [166.66 * 1.05 * 0.9 * (60 - 35)]/557.4
 = 7.06 MT/hr

iii) **Raw juice heating stage 3**
 = [166.66 * 1.05 * 0.9 * (75 - 60)]/548.2
 = 4.309 MT/ hr

$$5x + 111.66 = 135.619$$

$$x = 4.798$$

iv) **Sulphite juice heating stage 1**
 Quantity of Q₁ vapour required
 = [166.66 * 1.2 * 0.9 * (90 - 75)]/ 538.9
 = 5.01 MT/hr

1	2	3	4	5
62.24	50.00	9.219	9.219	4.7918
62240/ 2600	50000/ 3000	9219/ 1800	9219/ 900	4791.8/ 500
23.93*	16.66*	6.146*	10.24*	9.5836*

*- Evaporation rate

v) **Sulphite juice heating stage 2**
 Quantity of Q₂ vapour required
 = [166.66 * 1.2 * 0.9 * (102 - 90)]/532.4
 = 4.0569 MT/hr

Exhaust steam to Quintal / cal

$$= 62.24 * 100/166.66$$

$$= 37.34\% \text{ on cane}$$

vi) **Clear juice heating: stage 1 tubular heating**

Quantity of Q₁ vapour required
 = [166.66 * 1.05 * 0.9 * (105 - 95)]/526.4
 = 3.38 MT/hr

Line losses / condensation

$$= 1.0 \% \text{ on cane}$$

$$= 38.34\% \text{ on cane}$$

vii) **Clear juice heating**

Quantity of Q₁ vapour required
 = [166.66 * 0.9 * (118 - 105)]/530.4
 = 3.73MT/hr

Less condensate flash = 2.00

Exhaust Steam = 36.34% on cane

Total steam = 36.34 % on cane

Total vapour required per hour

$$= 0.40 \text{ MT/MT of mass}$$

5. Steam Balance For Radial Flow Evaporator

Steam input for evaporator effect 1= 57.70 T/hr

By Rieullix principle

Amount of vapour evaporated from effect 1

$$= 57.70 \text{ T/hr}$$

Steam bleeding used to heat clear juice

$$= 6.89 \text{ T/hr}$$

For PAN Washing

$$= 0.35 \text{ T/hr}$$

Steam supplied for effect 2

$$= 50.45 \text{ T/hr}$$

Steam bleeding from effect 2

$$= 30.21 \text{ T/hr}$$

Bleeding steam usage

For melter

$$= 0.3 \text{ T/hr}$$

Heating sulphited juice II = 5.76 T/hr

For Molasses Conditioning

$$= 1.0 \text{ T/hr}$$

For A-footing pan

$$= 6.23 \text{ T/hr}$$

For B-footing pan

$$= 2.45 \text{ T/hr}$$

For C-footing pan

$$= 2.0 \text{ T/hr}$$

Steam supplied for effect 3

$$= 20.24 \text{ T/hr}$$

Massecuite Quantities

A = 28% on cane 46.66 = 6.22 + 12.44 = 18.66 B =

11% on cane 18.33 = 2.44 + 4.888 = 7.332 C = 9 %

on cane 14.99 = 1.999 + 4.00 = 5.999

MT/hr 31.991

Steam utilized in pan boiling = 19.11% on cane

Assuming one third as footing / grain volume

Quantity of vapour required for A footing / grain boiling

$$= 18.66/3 = 6.22 \text{ MT/hr}$$

B footing / grain Quantities

$$= 7.32 / 3 = 2.444 \text{ MT/hr}$$

C footing / grain Quantities

$$= 5.999/3 = 1.999 \text{ MT/hr}$$

Clear juice Brix = 13.5,

Syrup Brix = 60

% Evaporation = (60 - 13.5)/60 = 77.5 % on cane

Quantity of water to be evaporated

$$= [166.66 * 1.05 * 0.775] = 135.619 \text{ MT/hr}$$

1	2	3	4	5
7.24	40.71	4.50	4.50	x
57.77	45.21	4.50	4.50	x

Figure 2. Steam balance for radial flow evaporator

Amount of steam sent to A- Continuous Vacuum pan
 = 12.46 T/hr

The vapors from effect 3 are sent to sulphite juice heating I, Effect 4, Continuous Vacuum Pan B & C.

Amount of steam sent to B- Continuous Vacuum pan
 = 4.9 T/hr

Amount of steam sent to C- Continuous Vacuum pan
 = 4.01 T/hr

Heat sulphited juice I = 5.42 T/hr
 For continuous pan B & C = 8.91 T/hr
 Steam supplied for effect 4 = 5.91 T/hr
 The vapors from effect 4 are used for raw juice III heating.
 For Raw juice heating III = 4.31 T/hr

Evaporated vapors used to heat raw juice III and sent effect 5.
 Steam supplied for effect 5 = 1.6 T/hr
 For Raw juice I heating
 The vapors evaporated here are used to heat raw juice 1 and the condensate is collected.

6. Steam Usage For Radial Type Evaporator

Basis: 4000 TCD

Working Hours = 4000/24 = 166.66 t/hr
 Mixed juice = 105%
 Sulphite juice = 120%
 Clear juice = 105%

i) **Raw juice heating stage 1**
 Quantity of vapour required

$$= [166.66 * 1.05 * 0.9 * (40 - 30)]/567.3$$

$$= 2.776 \text{ MT/hr}$$

ii) **Raw juice heating stage 2**
 Condensate heating at 35 - 60°C
 $= [166.66 * 1.05 * 0.9 * (60 - 35)]/557.4$
 = 7.06 MT/hr

iii) **Raw juice heating stage 3**
 $= [166.66 * 1.05 * 0.9 * (75 - 60)]/548.2$
 = 4.309 MT/hr

iv) **Sulphite juice heating stage 1**
 Quantity of Q₃ vapour required
 $= [166.66 * 1.2 * 0.9 * (90 - 75)]/538.9$
 = 5.01 MT/hr

v) **Sulphite juice heating stage 2**
 Quantity of Q₂ vapour required
 $= [166.66 * 1.2 * 0.9 * (102 - 90)]/532.4$ =
 4.0569 MT/hr

vi) **Clear juice heating stage 1 tubular heating**
 Quantity of Q₁ vapour required

$$= [166.66 * 1.05 * 0.9 * (105-95)]/526.4$$

$$= 2.9919 \text{ MT/hr}$$

vii) **Clear juice heating**
 Quantity of Q-1 vapour required
 $= [166.66 * 1.05 * 0.9 * (118-105)]/530.4$
 = 5.641 MT/hr

Total vapour required per hour
 = **0.40 MT/MT of mass**

viii) Masecuite Quantities

A = 28% on cane 46.66 = 6.22 + 12.44 = 18.66 B = 11% on cane 18.33 = 2.44 + 4.888 = 7.332 C = 9 % on cane 14.99 = 1.999 + 4.00 = 5.999

MT/hr 31.991

Steam utilized in pan boiling = 19.11% on cane
 Assuming one third as footing / grain volume

Quantity of vapour required for A footing / grain boiling
 = 18.66/3 = 6.22 MT/hr

B footing / grain Quantities
 = 7.32 / 3 = 2.444 MT/hr

C footing / grain Quantities
 = 5.999/3 = 1.999 MT/hr

Clear juice Brix = 13.5,
Syrup Brix = 60
% Evaporation = $(60 - 13.5)/60 = 77.5\%$ on cane

Quantity of water to be evaporated
= $[166.66 * 1.05 * 0.775] = 135.619$ MT/hr

Pressure distribution across the bodies

11/50 10.5/50 10/50 9.5/50 9/50

Vacuum in last body = 0.14 kg/cm^2 (Abs.Pre)

Pressure at first effect

= $2.2 - (2.06 * 11/50)$
= 1.7468 kg/cm^2

Pressure at second effect

= $1.7468(2.06 * 10.5/50)$
= 1.3142 kg/cm^2

Pressure at third effect

= $1.3142 - (2.06 * 10/50)$
= 0.90228 kg/cm^2

Pressure at fourth effect

= $0.9022 - (2.06 * 9.5/50)$
= 0.5314 kg/cm^2

Pressure at fifth effect

= $0.5108 - (2.06 * 9/50)$
= 0.14 kg/cm^2

Pressure kg/cm^2	Temperature $^{\circ}\text{C}$	Latent Heat J/kg K
2.2	122	524.4
1.9808	119	526.6
1.4852	110	532.4
1.0132	100	538.9
0.5648	84	548.8

1	2	3	4	5
7.24	30.2	14.33	5.91	x
57.77	50.45	20.24	5.91	x

$5x + 134.3 = 135.619$

$x = 0.2638$

1	2	3	4	5
57.96	50.713	20.503	6.173	0.263
57960/ 2000	50713/ 2300	20503/ 1800	6173/ 800	263/ 500
28.98*	22.04*	13.66*	7.71*	5.28*

*- Evaporation rate

Exhaust steam to Quintal / cal

= $57.94 * 100/166.66$
= 34.77% on cane

Line losses / condensation

= 1.0 % on cane
= 35.77

Less condensate flash = 2.00

Exhaust Steam = 33.77

Total steam = **33.77% on cane**

Conclusion

From the analysis of steam economy in sugar industry and other parameters in the radial flow the evaporator juice, condensate, vapour etc., move from outer periphery of calandria to the centre and the temperature difference is about 6°C in Radial flow evaporator when compared with that of the Robert type evaporator which is of 15°C . This was quite evident during the test phase. It is ease using radial type evaporators in place of Robert type evaporators which effectively reduce the steam usage in the process. Also the material and steam balance calculations, mass, steam flows are made. Users would definitely be at ease while working with this new system. The identical effects of each parameter are roughly evident. Still a detail study is established for better evaluation of performance by continuous observation. This novel design approach suggests that the rising film multi effect evaporator can be replaced by radial type multi effect evaporator, which can eliminate the disadvantaged caused by the rising film evaporator from the calculated results. This replacement modification fairly reduces the steam consumption in the process. So this modification shows that the steam economy can be enhanced in the large scale sugar industries of Ethiopia.

References

- [1] A.K. Ray and Pitam. Singh, "Simulation of Multiple Effect Evaporator for black Liquor Concentration", *IPPTA*, vol. 12(3), pp. 35-45, (2000).
- [2] A.R. Gupta, "Mathematical Modeling and analysis of pulp washing problems", *Ph.D Thesis, Indian Institute of Technology Roorkee*. (2001).
- [3] Angeletti S.M, Burton H, "Modeling of multiple effect evaporators" 1983.
- [4] Bhatt, B.I. & Vora S.M., 2004, "Stoichiometry", 4th Ed., *Tata McGraw-Hill Publishing Co. Ltd.*, New Delhi.
- [5] C.H. Runyon, T.R. Rumsey and K.L. McCarthy, "Dynamic simulation of a non-linear model of a double effect evaporator", *Journal of Food Engineering*, vol. 14, pp. 185-201, 1991.

- [6] Christie John Geankoplis, Transport Processes and separation process principles, 4th edition, *Prentice Hall India*.
- [7] Deepak kumar et al “Design of evaporator in paper industry using mathematical modeling” *International Journal of chemical & biological engineering*, Vol.3 (3), pp. 129-136, 2010.
- [8] Dhara J.Shah et al, “Design, modeling & simulation of multiple effect evaporators”, *International journal of scientific engineering & technology*, Vol.1 (3) pp. 1-5, 2012.
- [9] Evaporator handbook, 4th ed, *APV publishers*, 1996.
- [10] Farcy M et al, “A new control algorithm for concentration control in three effect falling film evaporators”, *Iranian journal of science & technology*, Vol. 33 (5), pp. 387-396, 2009.
- [11] Ghoshna Jyoti, “Design of heat integrated multiple effect evaporator system”, Master of Technology Research thesis, *National Institute of technology, Rourkela, India*, 2013.
- [12] H. Nishitani and E. Kunugita, “The optimal flow pattern of multiple effect evaporator systems” *Computers and Chemical Engineering*, vol. 3, pp. 261–268, 1979.
- [13] Kern D Q, Process heat transfer, *McGraw hill publication*, 1950.
- [14] Leena M.Borkar, “Software for single effect evaporator”, *International journal of advanced engineering research & studies*, Vol.2 (3), pp. 130-131, 2013.
- [15] McCabe, W.L., Smith J.C., Harriot P., 1993, Unit Operations of Chemical Engineering, 5th Ed., *McGraw Hill, USA*.
- [16] Minton P.E., 1986, Handbook of Evaporation Technology, *Noyes Publications, USA*.
- [17] Morgenroth B, Jayatilaka D et al, “Development of plate evaporator technology”, *Sugar Industries*, Vol.130, pp. 16–20, 1997.
- [18] Perry R.H. & Green D., 1984, Perry’s Chemical Engineer’s Handbook, 6th Ed., *McGraw Hill, USA*.
- [19] Prashant Balpande et al, “Thermal integration in multiple effect evaporator for zero steam consumption”, *International journal for engineering applications & technology*, Vol. 2 (1), pp. 138–142, 2013.
- [20] R.N. Lambert, D.D. Joye and F.W. Koko, “Design calculations for multiple effect evaporators. I. Linear methods”, *Industrial Engineering Chemistry Research*, vol. 26, pp. 100–104, 1987.
- [21] Raghuraman, “Design and simulation of a multiple evaporator system”, Master of Technology Research thesis, *National Institute of technology, Rourkela, India*, 2011.
- [22] S. Khanam and B.Mohanty, “Energy reduction schemes for multiple effect evaporator systems”, *Applied Energy*, vol. 87, pp.1102–1111, (2010).
- [23] Shabina Khanam et al, “Mathematical model for a multiple effect evaporator system”, *Indian journal of chemical technology*, Vol. 15, pp. 118-129, 2008.
- [24] Sinnott R.K., 2005, Chemical Engineering Design, 4th Ed., 6 Vol., Linacre House, *Jordan Hill, Oxford*.
- [25] Thakore S.B. & Bhatt B.I., 2007, “Introduction to Process Engineering and Design”, *Tata McGraw Hill Publishing Co. Ltd., New Delhi*.
- [26] Urbaniec K, Zalewski P et al, “Decomposition approach for the energy systems in the sugar industries”, *Applied thermal engineering*, Vol. 20, pp. 1431–1442, 2000

